

Knowledge and Skills: A Scrutiny of Methods of Teaching Foreign Language (English) in Secondary Schools of Uzbekistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 03, 2025</p> <p>Accepted: March 05, 2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Methodology; Teaching Foreign Language; Secondary School; School-Based Curriculum; Academic Results; Language Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18880018</p>	<p><i>This paper deeply analyses the methods of teaching foreign languages. The author (a) sets out the importance of methodology in teaching foreign language; (b) states the pros and cons of current teaching methods in a school-based curriculum; (c) calls attention to change the mindset of the teachers and using broader methods in teaching foreign languages; (d) suggests further approaches for superior academic outcomes. This study gathered data through field trip school observations, interviewing school teachers, teacher trainers, school principals, and parents, and analyzing available data. The qualitative research findings reveal dissatisfaction with the present methods and leading to poor academic achievements in the secondary schools of Uzbekistan except for private schools.</i></p>

Introduction

Along with developing countries, Uzbekistan - also heeds to teaching-learning foreign languages. On August 29, 1997, the IX session of the Oliy Majlis (Parliament) of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Law on Education and National Training Program, and in the tranquility of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No 1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" the essence of the process of educating well-rounded teachers and a qualified specialist is fully disclosed (World Bank Group, 2018).

During the Soviet Union era, in public schools, teachers were used to implementing traditional, priority of reading and writing, method of teaching foreign languages. The student-centered teaching system remains, even after the collapse of the Soviet empire, and shifts the role of the instructors from givers of information to facilitating student learning. Traditionally instructors focus on what they do, and not on what the students are learning.

Today, learning a foreign language in secondary schools of Uzbekistan aims to teach young learners to express their thoughts on social issues, personal information, leisure, occupations, sports, clothing, and brief descriptions of events and happenings in everyday life. Intensive methods of teaching a foreign language, bringing language skills to the level of the European standard B2 to C1 through the harmonious development of language skills, such as speaking, listening comprehension, reading, and writing are set as a primary purpose of the socio-economic development strategy of the Government, however, ongoing reforms and financing the education yet to pay off.

Literature review

The history of methods is a "war" between the new one with an existing one or an old one. Each method, rejecting the previous one, offers the only "best" approach to language learning and language teaching from its point of view. L.G. Kelly analyzes 25 centuries of foreign language teaching and philosophical approaches and methods that have existed in teaching foreign languages during this period (Frey & Kelly, 1971). L.G. Kelly studies the differences and similarities in approaches and teaching methods of different aspects of the language: speaking, reading, writing, as well as sub-skills: grammar and phonetics (Frey & Kelly, 1971). Here are some examples from Kelly's book of how methodological directions arise, disappear, and reappear.

In the time of the Roman Empire, language teachers were looking for answers to the same questions that we are trying to answer now. Kelly traces a direct method based on associations and connections between subject and word from St. Augustine (389 BC) (Frey & Kelly, 1971). St. Augustine wrote that if we hear a

sound, we do not understand whether it is a word, "until we know what this word means. Only when we establish a connection between objects, we understand the meaning" (Popović, 2019)(Mejzner, 2021). The Moravian Bishop Comenius (mid-17th century) believed that both the teacher and the students should be constantly involved in activities in the classroom, that after the teacher showed the rules or models, the students should actively practice them (Jackson, 2011). The same principle was used in the schools of Pestalozzi, who wrote that if a student hears a request to close the door, but does not see the door closing, learning does not take place (Sellars & Imig, 2020). In the 1970s, vols. Asher proposed a method of action based on this very principle (Rambe, 2019).

Demonstration and active participation were important principles of the natural method. Adherents of the natural method in the 19th century rejected the translation with the same confidence with which the supporters of the communicative approach in the 1980s rejected it in the 20th century (Rubin & Henderson, 1982).

Already at the beginning of the 20th-century supporters of the direct method used in teaching the realities encountered in everyday life - tickets, coins, stamps, and various texts, which again began to play the role of visual aids in the classroom (Rubin & Henderson, 1982). Gradually, this idea lost its relevance, since the main place was taken by texts written specifically for textbooks, and was revived only in the 80s when the movement of communicative competence developed.

It is interesting to follow, for example, the change in the attitude towards translation as a pedagogical method. Bilingual dictionaries became an integral part of classes only at the end of the 16th century. Before that, even in the schools of the Roman Empire, the method of the periphery was used. In the 19th century, the transfer method has become the standard teaching method (Rambe, 2019). And even the adherents of the direct method did not reject the translation at first and abandoned it completely quite late.

In the 1st century, BC Roman grammarians introduced words into context to demonstrate their meaning. In the 19th - 20th-century context by some authors was often replaced by separate sentences and in the late 80s adherents of communication, learning has fought to bring context back to textbooks and foreign language lessons (Красинская, 2011). At the beginning of the 20th century, Palmer objected to using only one method in language teaching and suggested combining different methods. And now people talk about the "post-methodical" period of teaching foreign languages with the use of mixed methodological techniques from different schools and directions (Красинская, 2011).

It can be seen that when creating new methods, elements of what has been done before are constantly used. Development proceeds as if in a spiral. The new spiral is now focusing on learning styles and strategies that take into account differences between learners. There has been a shift in focus from teaching to learning, from teacher to student. Based on an understanding of how individual students acquire a language (learning styles), and what is needed for assimilation to be more effective (learning strategies), modern approaches are built into the methodology.

Research question

As specified by the official sources, the Republic of Uzbekistan spends 43 percent of its budget on education (Izvorski et al., 2019), however, the quality of education and academic results are still ground-level compare to other developing countries. The big question remains on the answer.

1. Do the poor academic achievements in learning nonnative language depend on the fallacious method of teaching foreign language?

Theoretical framework

Definition of Methodology and Variety of Methods of teaching foreign language

The history of teaching foreign languages is a constant striving to find ways to quickly and efficiently master a foreign language. Intensive courses have always attracted and continue to attract students. The number of such courses increases dramatically every year. Many of them originate in the theory of G. Lozanov, a Bulgarian psychologist and teacher (QUIDER, 1932). His learning theory is known as Suggestopedia. Suggestopedia is a word of Greek origin and means "to offer something to someone, to present something at the disposal of someone." G. Lozanov (Китайгородская & Поляков, 2020), educational material - words, expressions, dialogues should be offered to the student in such a form and such conditions that he, having spent minimal physical and moral efforts, assimilated the maximum amount of information. For this, it is necessary to activate the reserve capabilities of a person, to help his memory work at full capacity. G. Lozanov proposes to "release" our capabilities, liberate our abilities, to turn on the mechanisms of memory with the help of specially organized classes. These activities are called sessions (sessions in Russian are called screenings of films, for example, morning and evening sessions, as well as treatment using hypnosis or hypnotist performances) (QUIDER, 1932). For 100 hours of classes in this method, students learn and can use up to 2000 words and expressions, can speak, read and even sing songs in a foreign language.

In suggestopedia, the text is read by the teacher, accompanied by classical music. The goal is better memorization of the text by students. Two types of musical sessions are used to memorize material: an active musical session and a pseudo-passive one.

Active session - reading the text in a musical rhythm. While reading, the teacher follows each musical phrase. Major mode - the phrase is pronounced joyfully, the minor mode - intimate lyrical reading, fast tempo - the phrase is read quickly, slow - slow reading, the music sounds quiet - the voice sounds quiet, etc. The polylogue phrase should end simultaneously with the musical phrase. During a pseudo passive (concert) session, the teacher pauses and starts reading the text. Moreover, the music sounds a little grottier than the teacher's voice, and the students are given the "Listen to music!"

The following works are recommended for musical sessions in the methodology: W. A. Mozart. Fifth Concerto for Violin and Orchestra in A major; J.S.Bach. Fantasia for Organ in G Major; F. J. Haydn. First Concerto for Violin and Orchestra in C major; G.F. Handel. Concerto for Organ and Orchestra in B flat major; Л. Beethoven. Concerto for violin and orchestra in D major; П. И. Чайковский ("Учимся учить - традиционный Юбилейный семинар учителей и преподавателей России и США. Старая Русса, 10 сентября 2016 г.," 2016)

Further work of the teacher is to teach students to communicate in a foreign language. The task is very difficult. The lesson must be taught in such a way that everyone speaks the way Russians speak in the theater, at home, on the street. This means that role-playing games are needed, an accurate description of what, where, and how to speak, with what intonations and gestures. If you are familiar with the work of actors, with how they say roles, act out scenes, then you will understand why the words "etude", "script", "dramatization" and "performance" are used when describing the lessons according to Lozanov (QUIDER, 1932).

Under the influence of this method, new schools and directions have developed in teaching foreign languages, and in particular Russian as a foreign language: activating the reserve capabilities of the individual (Китайгородская & Поляков, 2020).

Language is a system and structure of sounds, words, and constructions. A native speaker is proficient in this system, that is, has linguistic competence. Foreign language students must acquire knowledge of the language and learn to use this knowledge. If this is the ultimate goal of learning, we are dealing with a grammatical, structural direction in teaching. In this case, the teacher uses diagrams, tables, summarizes, represents the language system, and students learn words, make sentences, and conjugate, decline, translate. Language is not only a system and structure of forms but also their re-allegation in speech, which, in turn, has the rules of construction and use. Understanding the difference between language and speech was reflected in the teaching of foreign languages. The aim of the study was the formation of speech skills, that is, the ability to construct and understand many phrases through training, reproduction, and elaboration of source texts (models, samples). The main exercises were those manipulating sentences: transformation, substitution, rearrangement. All this is seen in the experience of direct, audiovisual, audiolingual teaching methods. Since the 70s language is considered not only in terms of language and speech but also in terms of communication, communication. The use of the linguistic structure and speech models in communication depends on who speaks to whom, when, for what purpose, that is, on non-linguistic factors that must also be studied, since without this the life of the language in society is impossible. The communicative description of the language led to the emergence of methods: group, natural, communicative, suggestopedic teaching of speech behavior. Typical of these methods are exercises that suggest solving non-linguistic goals by speech means (role-playing, business games, problem-solving, and problem situations development) (Annushkin, 2020). The problems of teaching a foreign language are studied by the methodology. Although people have studied foreign languages for centuries, the method of beginning has not evolved so long. Its development is closely related to applied linguistics, sociolinguistics, pedagogy, psychology. The problem of the methodology is quite wide: it turns off the description of the subject of teaching a foreign language, and the problem of psychology, defines learning technologies.

The problem of selection of speech material and its presentation in textbooks and educational audiences are considered, depending on:

- objectives of teaching
- training time
- learning density
- language proficiency

Explores how to present material to students, how to consolidate it, taking into account the types of students, how to bring students into natural communication.

In secondary schools of Uzbekistan, teachers mainly use an intensive method of teaching in the process of teaching students to speak a foreign language in a short period. This is largely based on the students' internal psychological capacity and memory (Shaturaev, 2014). Thus, the intensive method teaching has the following two characteristics:

1. Organize a certain amount of educational material in a short time and carry out appropriate speaking activities in a foreign language;

2. Maximizing the use of all the resources (psychological capabilities) of personal memory, i.e. increasing the activity of students.

Language is a system and structure of sounds, words, and constructions. A native speaker is proficient in this system, that is, has linguistic competence. Foreign language students must acquire knowledge of the language and learn to use this knowledge. If this is the ultimate goal of learning, we are dealing with a grammatical, structural direction in teaching. In this case, the teacher uses diagrams, tables, summarizes, represents the language system, and students learn words, make sentences, and conjugate, decline, translate. Language is not only a system and structure of forms but also their re-allegation in speech, which, in turn, has the rules of construction and use. Understanding the difference between language and speech was reflected in the teaching of foreign languages. The aim of the study was the formation of speech skills, that is, the ability to construct and understand many phrases through training, reproduction, and elaboration of source texts (models, samples). The main exercises were those manipulating sentences: transformation, substitution, rearrangement. All this is seen in the experience of direct, audiovisual, audiolingual teaching methods. Since the 70s. language is considered not only in terms of language and speech but also in terms of communication, communication (Московкин, 2012). The use of the linguistic structure and speech models in communication depends on who speaks to whom, when, for what purpose, that is, on non-linguistic factors that must also be studied, since without this the life of the language in society is impossible. The communicative description of the language led to the emergence of methods: group, natural, communicative, suggestopedic teaching of speech behavior.

The table below schematically depicts the teaching-learning scheme of a foreign language in public schools of Uzbekistan:

Typical of these methods are exercises that suggest solving non-linguistic goals by speech means (role-playing, business games, problem-solving and problem situations development) (Московкин, 2012).

So, three views on the nature of language lead to different methods. The learning objectives (step 1) determine the approach to teaching in each particular case, which has become especially noticeable recently: the creation of textbooks for the course and university audiences, for philologists and non-philologists, for businessmen, tourists, etc. In addition, they have published textbooks that emphasize speaking or listening, etc.

The use of the student's native language (step 3) characterizes the methods as follows.

1. Reliance on the native language, constant translation of words, phrases (translation-grammatical method).
2. The use of the native language is mainly for comparing linguistic and cultural phenomena and its limited use at the initial stage for explanation (cognitive, communicative methods).
3. Complete exclusion of the native language (direct, audiovisual, audiolingual, silent methods).

Presence/absence of language environment (step 4). Taking into account such differences led to the differentiation of concepts: the study of a foreign language - when the language is taught in the environment of the native language, and the study of a second language - when the language is taught in the environment of the target language. The selection of material, commenting, and lesson planning depends on the conditions under which the training is carried out. The teacher and students and their interaction (steps 5, 6) are also defined differently in the methods:

1. The teacher is the subject of the educational process; the student is the object of learning. This subordinate position of the student is reflected in most of the methods (audiolingual, audiovisual, translation-grammatical, method of action).
2. A student is an active subject of the educational process. The relationship between a student and a teacher as a subject-subject interaction (natural, communicative methods).
3. The student is the main figure of the educational process, the teacher is only an adviser, assistant (group, silent, suggestopedic methods, teaching speech behavior).

Control (step 8) is also carried out in different ways in the methods. There are supporters of strict control and avoidance of mistakes in the speech of students. There are supporters of soft control, but they are intolerant of mistakes. Finally, there are proponents of the denial of evaluative control who advocate for students' right to make mistakes.

Figure 1. Hypothesized Relative Contribution Model

Source: Higgs, T.,
The push toward
Assumptions led

& Clifford, R. (1982).
communication.

to the construction of a Hypothesized Relative Contribution Model (Figure 3), which posited fluctuating relative importance of subskill factors contributing to global language proficiency (Higgs & Clifford, 1982). Levels of global proficiency make up the horizontal axis of the model, while the vertical axis shows the hypothesized percentages or relative contributions of each subskill (Higgs & Clifford, 1982). In elucidating Figure 3, it is significant to adjudicate that the height of a curve at any given proficiency level shows correlative input into each subskill. The fact that the vocabulary curve drops as it approaches Level 5 does not mean that less vocabulary is needed, but that in comparison to the other four contributory skills, vocabulary declines in relative importance (Higgs & Clifford, 1982). At Level 1, vocabulary is hypothesized as the most pivotal component, meanwhile, grammar is ample to make up the language, and a ground-level of pronunciation is sufficiently accurate to be understood. Fluency—as measured in terms of words per minute—and sociolinguistic elements are not yet crucial, because at this level one is concerned with listeners who are used to dealing with foreigners, and the expectations of both the speaker and the listener are quite low (Higgs & Clifford, 1982).

In recent years, much needs to be done to increase student engagement in the classroom. One of the most important tasks is to create an environment of verbal communication to increase the activity of students in the classroom, using the internal capacity of personal memory. The methods used by the teacher and the various visual aids should be aimed at this goal. The psychological state of speech communication is one of the most important tasks in increasing the activity of students.

As claimed by the hypothesis, at Level 2, above mentioned connections would shift. The relative contribution of grammar would increase, as the required linguistic tasks (i.e., the range of linguistic functions to be mastered) became more complicated (Higgs & Clifford, 1982). The relative significance of pronunciation would start to decrease, simultaneously, after hitting the minimal level required to be understood, although few

students in academic language programs, including language majors, reach Level 3, government intensive language training programs often achieve this goal (Higgs & Clifford, 1982).

At Level 4, it was hypothesized that the curves would begin to coincide, as functional performance approached the level of the educated native speaker, who by definition would control each of these language aspects perfectly (Higgs & Clifford, 1982).

On the assumption that a person whose language was lacking in any one of these areas would not be judged to be an educated native speaker, we judged that all subskills would contribute equally to the global performance rating of Level 5, thus, all component curves converge at this level (Higgs & Clifford, 1982).

Research method

Data source & collection procedure

This qualitative research describes the enhancement of knowledge and language skills of Uzbek children through recent methods of teaching foreign languages in secondary schools. Data were collected in two stages. First, in March 2021, field trip observations at two public schools (School #110 in Shaykhontohur district and School #89 in Bektemir district) and two private schools (“Profi Study” in Mirabad district and Cambridge Tashkent School) in Tashkent city were conducted to explore the effectiveness and in use methods of teaching foreign language and teaching-learning process of the schoolchildren. Furthermore, 10 respondents from each school, 40 pupils in total, were involved in the questionnaire as well. Interviews were carried out in early May 2021, involving 25 people in total, including four (4) parents, three (3) school principals, and sixteen (16) teachers, and one (1) teacher trainer of the Education Center under the Ministry of Public Education and the Minister of the Public Education of the Republic was also associated. At the outset, the interviews were conducted in the Uzbek and Russian languages. Each interview is prolonged to 15-25 minutes, except the interview with the teacher trainer from the Ministry lasted for 60-80 minutes. Interviews with parents were conducted on the school campus. A brief interview with the Minister of Public Education, Sherzod Shermatov, was recorded at the Education Center under the Ministry. Following crosschecking, interview transcripts were translated from Uzbek and Russian into English for data presentation.

Data analysis

Lesson observations were conducted in all three (4) schools, teaching-learning processes were studied directly. The interviews were all audio-recorded, transcribed, and then analyzed. Etic and emic codes were used to analyze the interview data. The CAF (complexity, accuracy, and fluency) analysis method was used for scoring the audio data. A software Atlas.ti (version 8.4) was used to assist to analyze the data as well. Miles and Huberman model was used for providing visual reference how a collected data were tackled (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Findings and discussion

Findings of this qualitative study consist of the analysis of coeval methods of teaching a foreign language (English) in secondary schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Methods currently employed in teaching foreign language and indicators of student mastery

The government of Uzbekistan has recently started to focus on teaching-learning foreign languages at the primary level of schooling. Tests on the English language have now been included in the final exams of school gradulators and university entrance exams as well. Free and quality education is provided for primary and secondary schooling in Uzbekistan, however, now the government sets new settings in teaching foreign languages starting from kindergartens throughout the country. Integrating modern technologies in the teaching-learning process is believed as a key factor leading to higher academic outcomes. Meanwhile, most teachers still implement post-Soviet teaching methods for both teaching and learning foreign languages. However, private schools utilize up-to-date gadgets and effective methods in teaching integrating active learning styles. The school principal of “Profi study school” Jamila Kattayeva says:

We are unique in teaching foreign languages in the area. We have hired well-trained and experienced teachers, thus, it is high school fees in our school compare to public schools as pupils are provided good quality of education and conditions for young learners.

For 75 years, humility by the former Soviet Union has had a huge impact on education. The teacher-centered method of teaching is widely spread throughout most public schools, mostly in rural areas, is also the remnant model of the Soviet Union regime. Even there are hundreds of education projects are being launched, but still, low academic outcomes remain on the answer in the public education system. After the new presidential elections, a decree on establishing private schools was signed. However, it, currently, covers urban areas but the rural part of the country is yet to reach. Sherzod Shermatov, the Minister of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, says:

The uniforms are not the only issue we face at the moment. Teaching materials, teacher-training programs, disintegrating teaching methods are crucial problems that we have to deal with.

The choice of the path depends on many factors (where and with whom I speak, in what relationship I am with him/her, etc.). Having chosen the path, the speaker realizes his intentions in certain speech utterances or non-speech actions. If there is an intention to ask for food, it can be realized in speech as follows: 1) It would be nice to eat! 2) Give me something to eat; 3) Can I eat something? 4) Do we have any food? etc.

Table 2.

Source: A. Akishina 2002 "Learning foreign language".

Communicative foreign language training lesson model

Communicative teaching is not only a method of work, its organization but an integral system and even a philosophy of teaching, according to which language is understood as a means of communication that depends on both the speaker and the listener. The main task of this methodological direction is to teach students to participate in speech activity, that is, to teach them to solve the set goals by speech means.

1. Speech communication is a special type of speech activity in which goals and objectives lie outside the speech communication itself: Knowledge of a foreign language as a system of words and grammatical forms is not enough. This is not the goal of learning, but an intermediate link leading to verbal communication.
2. Speech communication - the ego's ability to perform much speech acts in various types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing): The core of communicative learning is exercises and assignments with the help of which students learn to correlate the goal of the activity with a speech utterance (if I want to take a book, I must (must) use the following statement: "Please give me a book"). A functional approach to the selection and presentation of the material is carried out at all levels.
3. Speech communication arises if there is a need for both the speaker and the listener: If students say, read, listen to the same thing, and then retell it, there is no communication (for example, tell each other the text that you have read! - non-communicative task).
4. The purpose of verbal communication very often lies outside the language. (I say because I want the partner to do some action.): Language proficiency is the ability of students to solve communication

problems. And the normalization of speech, the ability to use the desired form is an intermediate task of learning.

Principles of communicative learning

1. The unit of learning is not a word, not a phrase, but a speech act (for example, a request, disagreement, question, etc.). Students act out situations in which speech behavior is developed in various social situations. Behavior is determined by the social context.
2. Mastering a language is the formation of communicative competence, the ability to solve communication problems by speech means. The presence of linguistic and speech competence is considered an intermediate link. In the educational process, authentic materials are used, regional geographic concepts are introduced. Communication is conducted in the target language (the use of the native language is limited).
3. To communicate, you need to use classroom situations - to establish interpersonal communication. Hence the principle of the personal-active approach: students are involved in common activities (solve problems in groups, pairs). The teacher's role is to create and facilitate communication, not just to constantly correct mistakes.

Table 3.

Survey results by the school of respondents

School #110				School #89			
#	observed	expected	value hi	#	observed	expected	value hi
1	100%	100%	0.00	1	100%	100%	0.00
2	100%	100%	0.00	2	100%	90%	0.01
3	100%	100%	0.00	3	100%	80%	0.05
4	100%	92%	0.01	4	100%	82%	0.04
5	100%	70%	0.90	5	100%	70%	0.50
6	100%	40%	0.27	6	100%	50%	0.50
7	100%	60%	0.27	7	100%	50%	0.50
8	100%	70%	0.13	8	100%	75%	0.08
9	100%	70%	0.13	9	100%	73%	0.10
10	100%	90%	0.01	10	100%	72%	0.11
			1.71				1.89
Profi Study School				Cambridge Tashkent			
1	100%	90%	0.01	1	100%	90%	0.01
2	100%	80%	0.05	2	100%	80%	0.05
3	100%	91%	0.01	3	100%	90%	0.01
4	100%	92%	0.01	4	100%	72%	0.11
5	100%	70%	0.27	5	100%	70%	0.27
6	100%	40%	0.27	6	100%	60%	0.15
7	100%	60%	0.27	7	100%	68%	0.15
8	100%	65%	0.19	8	100%	75%	0.08
9	100%	78%	0.06	9	100%	70%	0.13
10	100%	80%	0.05	10	100%	80%	0.05
			1.18				1.01

This analysis reveals the essence of the research carried out for the selected two private and two public schools. Analyses of the data indicate that there is a need to improve the education sector, as the risk is deduced between the observed and expected values on the ground. The hi-index is significantly high in School #110 (1.71) and School #89 (1.89), while in Profi Study School and Cambridge Tashkent these indicators are higher than index one (tab.1 & fig.1.)

Chi-Square Goodness of Fit Test

In addition, unfortunately, such situations cannot provide systematic work on the development of speech skills based on various lexical and grammatical material. Therefore, it becomes necessary, in addition to using natural situations for educational purposes, to also use special educational speech situations. The educational speech situation consists primarily of the conditions of the situation and the speech reaction of students. In the context of the situation, the following components can be distinguished. Description of the situation, including information about both the situation and the participants in the conversation (for example, you are late for the theater. The ticket collector will not let you into the hall. Try to convince the ticket clerk to let you in, citing serious reasons for your lateness. Setting: theater; the performance has begun. Participants of the conversation: spectator and usher). Speech stimulus as a reason for promoting speech (in our case: your desire not to miss the first act of the play). A speech stimulus essentially means the attitude of the speakers to the situation, their specific position, which determines the direction, and often the design of speech. He does not always find his verbal expression in the text of the situation (situations with a latent speech stimulus are encountered), however, its presence in the context of the situation is mandatory. Speech can serve to achieve both speech and non-speech goals. In other words, we speak to solve all possible life tasks with the help of speech: for example, share knowledge with other people, convince them, manage their actions, express our own opinions and emotions, engage in work, etc. In the methodology, much attention is paid to motivating speech (how to make a student the need to speak), goal-setting (how to teach how to plan a speech to achieve goals), hence the following tasks appear in textbooks: "You are hungry, ask for food (in a restaurant, from a friend, etc.)". The most important thing for teaching is understanding the non-verbal motivation for verbal actions. This makes it possible to organize classes taking into account natural extracurricular situations. The school principal of Cambridge Tashkent, Dr. Haynes Miller, says that:

We do not care about uniforms. There is no sign of corruption over here. We were able to implement an international atmosphere over our international school. The primary aim of our academic staff is to teach school kids in the way they would prefer and enjoy the teaching-learning process. Thus, it can be seen the academic outcomes and students' achievements are higher than other primary schools in the area. There is always free space for self-development both for teachers and students as well. Putting results into main priorities will lead to outstanding records.

Data analysis by the Tableau method

Using the results of the survey, proposals for improving the sphere of education were also derived according to the following fig.2.

Fig. 2. Conclusions of respondents on improving local education.

Undoubtedly, there is a huge difference between public and private schools in the Republic. Investing an enormous amount of capital in self-development, conditions, library access, and teacher-training program abroad, hiring native speakersto pay out on the results. Parents are also grateful for the conditions created in private schools. Khomidov Fazliddin, a parent, says:

Before my child went to 1st grade, he only knew some words of English, so by the end of the school year, Islam, my son, is be able to express his thoughts in English. Now, he can ask questions, make up short conversations. I am so happy aboutthat. Of course, school fees are not cheap, but I am ready to use every opportunity to educate my child.

in such a case, it is difficult to encounter this situation in public schools. The reason is that the salaries of school teachers, the conditions in schools are not in good condition. The results of school students' mastering of English are also unsatisfactory. Annakulova Shakhnoza, a single mother, complained:

I cannot afford to send my child to a private school, so my child goes to a school close to our house. While at school, she memorizes new words in English, but she still can't speak in English.

There are several issues on teaching-learning the English language at primary level schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Over 10 years, the Government of Uzbekistan, trying to focus on the public education sector but has yet to achieve the planned results. However, the Uzbek teachers in each level, especially in primary and secondary education, have proved the method of teaching, well, that is “learning by doing.” Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan has established process-oriented methodology or system such as “student-centered learning” or “learning by doing” is to be introduced to develop trainability among students, it requires a long lead-time in which core professionals and functionaries are trained and given time to digest the new process. In 2011, with the help of UNICEF, there was a workshop held in Tashkent, which was aimed to bring new teaching methods in Uzbek schools which provided a chance for local Uzbek teachers to teach with a wide range of teaching-learning material types which include natural and direct sources such as movies and music, movements, flashcards, semi-structured conversations, and interactive role-playing situations. Under “No child left behind” or “Reaching the farthest areas” slogans new teaching methods such as mentioned above reaching every corner of the country year by year (UNISEF 2011). The first 10 minutes of the class is for checking home-works one by one, the next 10 minutes for the explanation of the topic, and the last 10 minutes of working individually in the class before giving home works. This kind of teaching does not ensure a silent classroom and bit hard to teach. Most of the Uzbek primary schools are yet to be equipped with up-to-date devices, therefore, teaching methods are still the traditional way of teaching with handbooks and given materials by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decision-makers have yet to focus on the core issue of the public education sphere.

Conclusion

We must be honest when talking about public education problems that we are facing at the moment. People like to argue that Uzbekistan has now its new life path after the last presidential elections. However, most of the tough community issues have not been tackled or unevenly supported by ‘decision makers’. I believe that education is the only way out of poverty, hence, most of the rural areas of the country have yet to have access to primary education. Poverty and disinvestment in primary education continue to undermine the quality of life in many inner-city neighborhoods, and their ill effects have begun to affect some older suburbs as well. These conditions affect not only current living conditions in those neighborhoods but also the life chances of community residents and the social health of the cities. Educational policies in Uzbekistan over the years have shown that our policymakers have either not understood the problems of primary education. They are attracted to and trapped in urban “cores” which generate and communicate their sort of knowledge which community “peripheries” are isolated and neglected. Some steps have been taken, in the public education system by authorities but still crucial ones are remaining untouched. For instance, lack of motivation on both pupils and teachers, low quality of the teaching-learning process, poor access to compulsory education cause awful issues in the country.

Putting into account research results, the final picture can be drawn:

- **Excessive student relationship with the teacher**

If students do not know the correct answers to some of the questions, they are silently waiting for the teacher to give the correct answer. I see this behavior as a feeling of not believing in the answer, rather than knowing that the answer is correct. Every English teacher should encourage students to reduce such situations and to help them think independently as much as possible. Inspiration is very important in this situation because it increases the student's self-confidence.

- **Make the most of mother tongue**

It is possible to teach in this way in large classes of the school, especially with graduates, but I think it is impossible to teach English with young learners without using Uzbek. However, excessive use of the first language (mother tongue) can also be a major barrier to students learning a foreign language. There should be a balance between the teacher's use of English and Uzbek in the classroom during English lessons. But how do you find that standard? If Uzbek is spoken a lot, it seems that English is not spoken enough to students. Conversely, if a lot of English is spoken and as a result, students do not understand what they are talking about, they may not be able to fully understand some of the assignments. In any case, the problem with the norm of language use in classes between native speakers and English, I think, concerns most teachers.

- **Boring lessons, old-fashioned teaching methods, and leaving the weaker students behind**

This situation should not be allowed in English classes, as it makes students always different and always makes them second. Everyone should participate equally in English classes and learn equally. While some students who are more knowledgeable than others may be given good grades in the classroom and a certain amount of incentives, it is important to keep in mind students who are slower to learn or who are not fully involved in the class. They need to be encouraged more than others and allowed to take an active part in the lesson. Most teachers, especially in public schools, waste students' time. A boring, unprepared lesson, using the Soviet Union method of teaching is just corruption but nothing else.

There is not yet a clear national strategy for community development to match the growing requirements for community engagement in governance and public education. As a solution above elicited issues in the sphere of public education can be found far in the west. Implementing Finnish primary education development policies. Hiring native speakers in teaching-learning foreign languages, especially English language, zero corruption, inviting specialists in the sphere, cooperate in scientific projects on enhancing the quality of education, learning the language will lead to better academic outcomes in the upcoming future. These actively tackle the division, social exclusion, and discrimination that deter decision-makers on the development of public education in Uzbekistan.

Limitation

The study has some limitations despite the findings. The number of participants in the study was limited, in addition, a primary school in rural areas is yet to be covered. Thus, researchers should take into consideration involving wider geography for future studies to draw a picture comprehensively.

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